

SALES FORECASTING UNVEILED: ITS EFFECT ON ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS IN THE NIGERIAN BAKERY INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Sales forecasting is a crucial aspect of organizational planning, enabling managers to anticipate and plan for future demand, control costs, and improve logistics operations. However, many organizations struggle with sales forecasting planning and process, resulting in choosing the wrong sales forecasting technique and failing to accurately predict future sales, which can have detrimental effects on organizational performance. This study focuses on the bread-making industry in Nigeria and analyzes the impact of sales forecasting on organizational performance, using both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies to analyze data gathered from the field. The study reveals that all dimensions of sales forecasting positively affect organizational performance and recommends that organizations have a sound sales plan, develop effective and efficient sales processes, and monitor the activities of salespeople to improve sales forecasting decision-making processes. This document also includes a literature review on the concepts of sales forecasting, sales planning, sales process, salespeople's activities, and sales performance, providing a comprehensive understanding of the importance of sales forecasting in the growth and development of organizations.

KEYWORDS

Sales forecasting, organizational planning, demand, logistics, predicting sales.

INTRODUCTION

The important aspect of a successful marketing planning is forecasting the demand for a product (Halmet & Singh, 2015). All business firms would like to know the current as well as the likely demand for their products and how much of the given product they would be selling in a given market in a given period; whether the sales would increase or decrease from the current levels and by how much; and what would be their market share (Chambers, 2017). This knowledge is very essential for a firm. Without this knowledge, it cannot plan any of its activities. Demand measurement and sales forecasting provides this vital knowledge.

The process of sales forecasting entails estimating the sales of a product during some future time period (Hibon & Evgeniou, 2015). The result of demand forecasting is the preparation of sales forecast, usually for a one-year period. A sales forecast is the foundation of all budgeting and operational planning in all departments of a company. The sales forecasting applied on sales and productivity helps in providing the manager with the basis on how he can plan the future, the nature of future sales, how sales can affect the production decisions and what will be the sales functions of the organization (Akrani, 2011).

Polanski (2017) posited that sales forecasting is basically concerned with making predictions about future sales. Firms must anticipate and plan for future demand so that they can react immediately to customers' orders as they are made. The ability to accurately make sales forecast enables firms to control costs by leveling

their production quantities, rationalizing their transportation and planning for efficient logistics operations. Accurate forecasts lead to efficient operations and high levels of customer service which influences business performance (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2013).

Sales forecasting refers to the utilization of the gathered and interpreted information in decision making. Through sales forecasting, the intangible information and knowledge is turned into visible marketing actions. Chindia (2016) underlined that the processes for market-sensing are more systematic, thoughtful, and anticipatory in market-oriented firms than they are in other firms, in which these processes tend to be ad hoc, reactive, constrained, and diffuse. According to Chindia (2016), it can be assumed that organizations that have mastered the market-sensing activities gain competitive advantage and superior business performance. In other words, an organization's ability to learn about its market environment and use this information appropriately to guide its actions is the key driver of business performance (Smith, 2010; Zhang, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

A great number of organizations have failed in their sales forecast planning and process that provide them the required and accurate sales forecasting result. The problems associated with sales forecasting planning and process and the activities of the sales people in enhancing the sales forecasting decisions of the organisations have been difficult for some organizations to identify. These challenges have led them to choosing the wrong sales forecasting technique and as a result, they fail. The major problem associated with sales forecasting is the problem of knowing the historic data of that particular event on which one is basing his sales forecast. This is so because many sales forecast depend on historic data.

There is also the problem of selecting the accurate sales forecast technique that goes with time. This means that the sales forecast has to be timely and at the same time accurate. This problem is so alarming because the organization that wrongly chooses the inaccurate sales forecast will have a devastating negative effect. The result cannot be reliable and cost is also incurred. This study will therefore make a close evaluation of the sales forecast on future sales and productivity, most especially, in the bakery industry. It will highlight the knowledge deficiency in sales planning and process formulation and how best they can monitor the activities of sales people that can help to improve sales forecasting decision making process of managements. The study will help in providing an array of empirical evidence that business owners in the industry can adopt in facilitating their sales forecasting decisions that are accurate and timely, in order to enhance their future sales forecasting planning, process and efficiency.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to determine the effect of sales forecasting on sales performance of some selected bakeries in Asaba, Delta State. Specifically, the objectives are:

1. To determine the effect of sales planning on sales volume
2. To examine the role of sales process on market size
3. To examine the effect of salespeople's activities on market share.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses have been formulated to guide this study in a null form:

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between sales planning and sales volume.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between sales process and market size.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between salespeople's activities and market share.

LITERATURE REVIEW Conceptual Review The Concept of Sales Forecasting

Singh (2016) defined sales forecasting as a projection into the future of expected demand, given a stated set of environmental conditions. Chase (2013) postulated that sales forecasting refers to predicting future demand (or sales), assuming that the factors which affected demand in the past and are affecting the present, and will

still have an influence in the future. Sales forecasting is a process of predicting what the company's future sales are likely to be (Small Business Development Corporation, 2015). Harles (2013) opined that sales forecasts are estimates or predictions of organisational sales activities for the forecast period. Oftentimes, this prediction is based upon past sales performance of the product or service. Generally, sales forecasting is the art or science of predicting future demand by anticipating what consumers are likely to do in a given set of circumstances.

Sales forecasting helps investors to make decisions about investments in new ventures. It helps in predicting the amount people will purchase, given the product features and the conditions of the sale. They are vital to the efficient operation of the firm and can aid managers on decision making as to the size of a plant to build, the amount of inventory to carry, the number of workers to hire, the amount of advertising to place, the proper price to charge, and the salaries to pay salespeople (Smith, 2010; Chindia, 2016). Sales forecasting can be used by managements through different factors (e.g., sales history, sales promotion, seasonality, and so on) to predict future sales and then use information from the forecast to develop plans for resources and capacity to meet demand in the best possible way (Jonsson & Mattson, 2011). Sales forecasting can also be used in significant managerial decision-making within companies (Moon, 2013).

The Concept of Sales Planning and Sales Volume

A sales plan is a strategy that sets out sales targets and tactics for business, and identifies the steps that will be taken to meet the targets (Randall & Gilles, 2015). A sales plan helps organisations to define a set of sales targets for their business, choose sales strategies that are suitable to the target market and identify sales tactics for organisational sales team. Sales planning is important for any organisation that intend to drive sales volume (Lakhani & Kleiner, 2014). This is because it helps organisations to foresee potential risks so that they can try to mitigate them beforehand. It not only helps organisations to formulate a strategic plan but also puts them in control by helping them determine their product's current status, where they want to take it, and how they will get there (Azizi, Hossini &Roosta, 2012).

Sales planning plays an important role when a product is being offered in a variety of markets. It helps organisations devise strategies according to the culture, needs, and requirements of each consumer (Needorn, 2019). This is because a sales plan sits within, or alongside, a marketing plan to direct the efforts of the sales team. Without a sales strategy plan in place, salesmen and managers will make decisions based on what is in front of them at that given time (Harles, 2013). Not because they are careless but rather because they are unaware of the company's long-term goals. As a result, it becomes challenging to attach sales activity to specific data-backed objectives. This therefore means that to create dependable, long-lasting growth throughout for the organisation, sales managers need a sales strategy (Rombe, 2018).

The Concept of Sales Process and Market Size

Sales process is a set of repeatable steps that salespeople take to make a prospective buyer from the early state of awareness to the closed sales (Zarema, 2020). Olannye (2013) postulated that there are eight stages in the sales process: prospecting, pre-approach, approach, sales presentation and demonstration, handling customer objectives, closing the sales, departure and follow up. However, he added that the actual activities undertaken within each stages of the process will vary from organisation to organisation and also between salespeople. The sales process may also be longer or shorter depending on the nature of the product/service and the characteristics of the market.

Currie and Rowley (2010) opined that sales process is the most important process to provide data for sales forecasting. It provides data on what is happening in the sales pipeline. Sales pipeline describes the individual steps salespeople take from the initial contact to a potential customer or a prospect (Jordan & Kelly, 2015). All prospects are stored in the sales pipeline. Sales pipeline provides the data on how the prospects are moving

forward. When the prospect has moved to the qualified opportunity, it has certain probabilities to increase sales in the future.

The Concept of Salespeople's Activities and Market Share

Today, the role of a salesperson has become an even more critical one. It has evolved from implementing the selling function to become a core value creator for customers and sales organisations (Zhang & Glynn, 2015). In addition, organisations require their salespeople to deal with increasingly complex sales situations, persuade buyers within increasingly competitive environments, build trust and achieve overall organisational sales goals in order to increase organisational market share (Franklin & Marshall, 2018). Given the importance of a salesperson's performance, organisations should focus on identifying a broad spectrum of components that affect the performance of salespeople. A salesperson will personally communicate the company's product/service values to their customers (Schwepker & Ingram 2016). It is the salesperson who personally understands what their customers want and need. A salesperson is often the only representative of the organization seen by the customers. Hence, the salesperson's focus is on satisfying the customers' needs.

The Concept of Sales Performance

Sales performance is the effectiveness of the sales team, both individually and as a team, in selling activities and the ability to achieve sales target. Sales performance can be measured in a variety of ways depending on the sales role and sales environment, such as sales revenue, customer retention rate, or number of net new accounts. Sales performance is the measurement of sales activities against the goals outlined in the sales plan. The simplest method of tackling sales performance is to establish sales goals for the sales team and individual sales team members (Jason, 2019). This is influenced by the skills, ability, knowledge, competencies, and experiences of the sales teams in the organization. Measuring sales performance is vital in any organisation and it serves as a tool to understand where the organisation stands. It is crucial to keep this focus in mind to enable the organisation to better service employees, owners and customers (Johnson, 2010).

Effects of Sales Forecasting on Sales Performance

Sales forecasting is very important and critical to the effectiveness, growth, and survival of organisations. This goes to say that the importance of sales forecasting cannot be overemphasized in the management of business enterprises today. The ability to anticipate and satisfy customers' demand is very necessary for any profitable business (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2013). Companies invest time, money and effort for having the goods and services available in the right place and at the right time. The companies must invest in planning and forecasting processes, technology systems, methods and metrics, inventories and business analytics. These types of efforts are necessary for improving their ability to improve business sales projections. (Lawless, 2014).

A sales forecast serves as an effective planning in the company. Companies make financial decisions based on the forecasts. Sales forecasting is a business discipline which can be found in marketing, operations, strategic planning, and finance. As Chase and Charles (2014) stated, making the best possible sales forecast using data that are readily available can help businesses provide consumers with the right product. Forecasting helps change data into information which can help businesses become more profitable. Thus, sales forecasting knowledge and ability should be an essential skill set of all marketing managers. This is so because sales forecasting is a crucial issue for companies as several activities and decisions within a firm are based on forecasts (Lakhani & Kleiner, 2014). These encompass strategic planning, financial analyses, promotion management or new product launches.

Conceptual Framework

Sales Forecasting

Empirical Review

Haataja (2016) investigated the effect of Sales Forecasting on Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises which provide software services and applications to their business customers. The theoretical framework of the study focused on two essential components: sales forecasting processes in SMEs and forecasting tools. A total of 13 tools were selected for a detailed examination. In addition, four sales directors were interviewed in order to examine how sales forecasting is applied in their respective companies and the kind of challenges they were facing in sales forecasting. Semi-structured questionnaire was used in the interviews. The findings of the study revealed a significant relationship among the variables tested. The study recommended the need for SMEs to always analyze sales forecasting and develop sales forecasting capabilities.

Pamela and Matteo (2011) investigated the impact of sales forecasting on companies' performance: Analysis in a Multivariate Setting. The aim of the study was to investigate what relevant sales forecasting variables should be considered to improve companies' performance, and whether some forecasting variables can interact and influence performance with a synergistic effect. Analyses were conducted by means of data collected by the Global Manufacturing Research Group (GMRG). Data from a sample of 343 manufacturing companies in six different countries demonstrated that when companies intend to improve cost and delivery performances, they should devote their attention to all the different sales forecasting variables. In addition, the results revealed the existence of positive interaction effects between the collection and use of information on the market and the other forecasting variables, as well as the existence of a negative interaction effect between the adoption of sales forecasting in several decision making processes. The study therefore recommended that managers should always leverage on the different sales forecasting variables during decision making to maximize companies' performance.

Rombe (2018) investigated the effect of effective sales forecasting in relation to business growth in South Sudan. The main aim of this study was to examine the scientific application of sales forecasting in modern business and to prove its effectiveness on business growth. Different sales forecasting was applied in this study to determine the correlation. The multiple methodologies (combination of face to face interviews and structured questionnaires) were used to collect relevant data. Sample sizes of sixty-one (61) businesses were taken for the study. Statistical package for social sciences (SSPS) for data analysis was applied. The cross-data statistics suggested that there is strong correlation between sales forecasting and business growth in the given market and most business sales forecasting are based on the length of experience and subjective managers' judgments.

Needorn (2019) examined the effect of sales forecasting on organizational performance: The Nigerian Manufacturing Sector Experience. To put the study in perspective, seven hypotheses were drawn from

reviewed literature and dimensions and measures of the subject therein. These hypotheses were analyzed using Kendall Tau B statistics. The findings reveal that a significant relationship exists between all measures of sales forecasting and dimension of organizational performance. Thus, organizational performance can be manipulated through the regulation of the dimension of organizational performance. Consequently, the findings of the study recommended that efforts should be made by the organization to ensure accuracy of sales forecasting as much as possible since inaccurate forecasts can lead to misleading results. Planning in the organization should be based on the analysis of sales forecast outcome.

Hill (2014) evaluated the sales forecasting techniques applied in the manufacturing industry. The objectives of the research were to evaluate the demand forecasting method used by the manufacturing company, analyse the sales data of the company using several forecasting methods, and lastly, propose the most suitable sales forecasting method to the manufacturing company. The forecasting method was assessed by using forecast error measurement tools, such as Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and Tracking Signal. These forecast error analyses were used to monitor the forecast result of various methods. The result of this study showed that trend projection was chosen as the most suitable forecasting method as it produces the most accurate result and least forecast error. Sales forecasting plays a critical role in every business, especially in the manufacturing industry. Most of the operations decisions in the manufacturing industry are based on some kind of sales forecast for future demand. As a result, the study recommended that manufacturing companies should pay high attention towards sales forecasting in their business decision making process.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study was the survey research design used to assess the relationship between sales forecasting and sales performance. This is therefore quantitative in nature. This design was selected because it comprises a cross-sectional design in relation to which data are collected predominantly by questionnaire and at a single point in time in order to collect a body of quantitative or quantifiable data in connection with two or more variables which are then examined to detect patterns of association.

The population of this study consisted of all the staff of some selected bakeries. The selected bakeries that made up the total population of the study were Bonaac Bakery, Kingdom Bread Bakery and Maggi Bread all in Asaba, Delta State. These people were chosen because they have indebt understanding of the sales activities of the firms. The population was made up of 86 (eighty-six) employees. The entire list of the population was obtained from the administrative department where all staff records are kept.

Since the population was not too large, the study used the whole population for the study as the sample. A sample size of eighty-five (85) respondents was therefore chosen for the study. The simple random sampling technique was used because it allows for the possibility of every member of the population to be included in the survey study.

In this research, data were collected from primary sources and secondary sources. The secondary data collected were from the internet, journals and other published materials used to provide additional information to make the study fruitful. The primary data collected was through questionnaires. The questionnaire is in two sections: A and B. Section A is the personal data of the respondents while section B was used to get information on the variables selected for the study. The questionnaire is in four responses of the modified Likert scaling of five (5) point closed ended questions, which are: 5 = Strongly Agreed, 4 = Agreed, 3 = Undecided, 2 = Disagreed, and 1 = Strongly Disagreed.

Descriptive statistics was used in analyzing the data. It involves the computation of frequency distribution, mean and standard deviation, etc. which are useful to identify differences among groups. In order to meet the

objectives of this study, all valid responses from the formulated hypotheses were assessed using the linear regression analysis through statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 22.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSIONS Test of Hypotheses

The regression analysis was employed as the statistical tool for testing the hypotheses formulated for the study. The decision rule stipulates that the null hypotheses will be accepted if the p-value (calculated value) is greater than the set level of significance (critical value) of 0.05 (5%) and rejected (i.e., accepting the alternate) if it is less than the critical value.

Test of Hypothesis One

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between sales planning and sales volume.

Table 1: Model Summary Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.888 ^a	.776	.775	.90616

a. Predictors: (Constant), sales planning

The result from the table above shows that changes in sales planning is brought about by 77% (.776) as exhibited by the adjusted R² value. This implies that the independent variables explained 77.6% of the variability of the dependent variable.

Table 2: Fitness of the Model ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2248.749	1	2248.749	2738.610	.000 ^b
Residual Total	55.837	68	.821		
	2304.586	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Sales volume

b. Predictors: (Constant), sales planning

The result from the table above shows the *F*-ratio test whether or not the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table indicated that sales planning statistically significantly predicts sales volume, *F* (1, 69) = 2738.610, and *p* < .0005 (this indicates that the regression model is a good fit for the model).

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Sales Planning on Sales Volume Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1 (Constant)	-.091	.231		-.394	.695
sales planning	1.009	.019	.988	52.332	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sales volume

The table above shows that the critical value of .000 is less than the p-value of .05 as the R adjusted (Adj. r²) value bears a positive value of .776, showing the strength of the relationship. Therefore, the null hypothesis

is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between sales planning and sales volume, is thereby accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Two

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between sales process and market size.

Table 4: Model Summary Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.985 ^a	.970	.970	1.00619

a. Predictors: (Constant), sales process

The result from the table above shows that changes in sales process is brought about by 97% (.970) as exhibited by the adjusted R² value. This implies that the independent variables explained 97% of the variability of the dependent variable.

Table 5: Fitness of the Model ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2235.742	1	2235.742	2208.329	.000 ^b
	Residual	68.844	68	1.012		
	Total	2304.586	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Market size

b. Predictors: (Constant), sales process

The result from the table above shows the *F*-ratio test whether or not the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table indicated that the sales process statistically significantly predicts market size, *F* (1, 69) = 2208.329, and *p* < .0005 (this indicates that the regression model is a good fit for the model).

Table 6: Regression Analysis of Sales Process on Market Size Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	-1.007	.275		-3.660	.000
	sales process	1.011	.022	.985	46.993	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Market size

The result from the table above shows that the critical value of .000 is less than the *p*-value of .05 as the *R* adjusted (Adj. *r*²) value bears a positive value of .970, showing the strength of the relationship. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between sales process and market size, is thereby accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Three

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between sales people activities and market share.

Table 7: Model Summary Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.988 ^a	.876	.876	.89602

a. Predictors: (Constant), salespeople activities

The result from the table above shows that changes in salespeople’s activities are brought about by 87% (.876) as exhibited by the adjusted R² value. This implies that the independent variables explained 87% of the variability of the dependent variable.

Table 8: Fitness of the Model ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2249.992	1	2249.992	2802.521	.000 ^b
Residual	54.594	68	.803		
Total	2304.586	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Market Share

b. Predictors: (Constant), salespeople activities

The result from the table above shows the *F*- ratio test whether or not the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table indicated that salespeoples’ activities statistically significantly predict market share, *F* (1, 69) = 2802.521, and *p* < .0005. This indicates that the regression model is a good fit for the model.

Table 9: Regression Analysis of Salespeople’s Activities on Market Share Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-.294	.232		-1.264	.210
salespeople activities	1.047	.020	.988	52.939	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Market Share

The result from the table above shows that the critical value of .000 is lesser than the *p*-value of .05 as the *R* adjusted (Adj. *r*²) value bears a positive value of .876, showing the strength of the relationship. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between salespeople’s activities and market share, is thereby accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The aim of this study was to examine the effect of sales forecasting on sales performance of some selected bakeries in Asaba. Specifically, the study seeks to determine how sales planning sales, process sales and people’s activities influence sales performance. The data used for the study were collected primarily through the administering of structured questionnaires. The data were presented and analyzed using the regression statistical tool. From the result that was revealed and discussed, below are summaries of the major research findings:

From the result of hypothesis one, the critical value of .000 was observed to be less than the *p*value of 0.05 as the *R* adjusted (Adj. *r*²) value bears a positive value of 0.775, showing the strength of the relationship. By this, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant relationship between sales planning and sales volume, was rejected. This finding aligns with the findings of Scott (2010), who reported a positive relationship between sales planning and sales volume. He argued that effective sales planning helps organisations to define a set of sales targets for their business, choose sales strategies that are suitable to the target market and identify sales tactics for organisational sales teams.

From the result of hypothesis two, the critical value of .000 was observed to be less than the pvalue of 0.05 as the R adjusted (Adj. r^2) value bears a positive value of .970, showing the strength of the relationship. By this, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant relationship between sales process and market size, was rejected. This finding aligns with the findings of Currie and Rowley (2010), who reported a positive relationship between sales process and market size. They argued that a well-defined sales process allows organisations to better understand every stage of the sales pipeline, develop more effective sales and marketing strategies, move prospects along the buying process more quickly and smoothly onboard new hires when expanding their sales team.

From the result of hypothesis three, the critical value of .000 was observed to be less than the p-value of 0.05 as the R adjusted (Adj. r^2) value bears a positive value of .876, showing the strength of the relationship. By this, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between sales people activities and market share, was rejected. This finding aligns with the findings of Zhang and Glynn (2015), who postulated organisations should use salespeople to deal with increasingly complex sales situations, persuade buyers within increasingly competitive environments, build trust and achieve overall organisational sales goals in order to increase organisational market share.

CONCLUSION

Sales forecasting is not a one stop shop for organizational solutions. As it is commonly said, it is not a crystal ball to see exactly what will happen to the market over the coming years, but it will help give a picture of what is to come. Generally, it is concluded that sales forecasting is a positive and significantly viable tool for the improvement of performance of sales persons. Specifically, the paper concludes the following:

Firstly, the paper concluded that sales planning has a positive and significant effect on the volume of sales that will be made by an organization if properly appropriated. This will provide organisations with a sense of direction which will allow management to get the most out of the marketplace.

Secondly, sales process has a positive and significant effect on sales performance of the organization. It reduces the difficulty of predicting the future. By establishing a viable sales process, organisations can predict future trends and then change their company objectives to achieve success even in a depressed and competitive industry. Finally, salespeople's activities have a positive and significant effect on sales performance. Given the wide swings in economic activity and the drastic effects these fluctuations can have on profit margins, it is not surprising that salespeople management has emerged as one of the most important aspects of corporate planning. Good management of salespeople activities helps business owners and managers adapt to a changing competitive industry.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of findings, the following are recommendations for future implementation:

1. Organizations should have a good sales plan in place as it will not only help them to formulate a strategic plan but it will also put them in control by helping them determine their product's current status, where they want to take it, and how they will get there.
2. Organizations should develop an effective and efficient sales process as it will provide them data on what is happening in the sales pipeline.
3. Since salespeople are the face of the organisation and the representatives of the organization seen by the customers, management should often emphasize proper recruiting, training and managing of their salespeople by developing effective frameworks for them.

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